

FELLOWSHIP

MAY 2026

Bhilai

City Vision Document

A citizen-led vision narrative capturing stories, concerns, and hopes for the city's future

About the Vision Document

This City Vision Document is a reflective learning assignment carried out as part of the Nāgrika Fellowship Programme. It is based on a limited number of conversations with citizens and observational research conducted over a few months by the fellow. The document does not claim to represent the complete or official vision of the city, but rather offers a citizen-led snapshot—built through individual stories, insights, and lived experiences gathered during the fellowship. The perspectives shared here reflect the voices of a few residents, selected to capture a range of age groups, professions, and neighborhoods. The document is not exhaustive and may not include all communities or viewpoints. This document is intended as a starting point for dialogue and reflection. We hope it encourages broader conversations about the city’s identity, challenges, and future possibilities.

The research and writing were undertaken independently by the fellow, within a framework of structured guidance provided by Nāgrika. This included thematic prompts, narrative-building exercises, regular mentorship and feedback sessions, all designed to support the fellow in shaping their city’s vision. The interpretations and final content remain those of the fellow.

Nāgrika does not independently verify all the facts or statements in this document and does not assume responsibility for any errors, inaccuracies, or inconsistencies. The use of Nāgrika’s branding denotes the document’s origin within a guided fellowship process, not an endorsement of specific content. The document has been formatted by Nāgrika for presentation consistency; no edits have been made to the fellow’s original content. All images used in this document are sourced from the author themselves, in case otherwise credited.

© 2026 Nāgrika Policy Research Foundation.

This City Vision Document was created by the fellow-author as part of the Nāgrika Fellowship Programme and published by Nāgrika Policy Research Foundation. It is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International Public License. Please credit the fellow-author and Nāgrika Policy Research Foundation when using or citing this document.

This document was partly supported by Rohini Nilekani Philanthropies. Images are included under the same licence unless separately credited or stated otherwise

This document is archived and citable via DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20028438>

Nāgrika Fellowship

The **Nāgrika Fellowship Programme** has been designed to empower young individuals from diverse educational and geographic backgrounds, including students, gap-year participants, and early-career researchers, to positively engage with the history, socio-economic, governance, and cultural context of their cities. Focused on the youth of small and mid-sized cities, the fellowship is building local knowledge, enabling civic consciousness, and developing thought leaders who can address environmental, social, and infrastructural challenges. Over a period of six months, fellows gained tools for understanding and engaging with their cities.

A key component of the fellowship is the development of the **City Vision Document** by the fellows. This document is an emotionally grounded reflection of how citizens experience and imagine their city. Developed through conversations with diverse residents of the fellows' cities, it weaves together stories of everyday life, places of belonging, pressing concerns, and aspirations for the future. The document captures lived experiences and heartfelt insights to build a narrative that is authentic, accessible, and community-driven. It serves not only as a record of local voices but also as an invitation to reimagine the city through the eyes of those who call it home.

Contents

03	About the Fellowship
05	Why this Vision Document
07	Meet Bhilai
10	Glossary
11	Everyday Life
15	Places of Belonging
20	Voices of Concern
26	Dreams for Tomorrow
29	Policy Insights
34	About the Fellow
35	Message from Founders

Everyday Life

This theme explores the daily rhythms, routines, and interactions that shape how people experience their city. It highlights the ordinary yet meaningful details of our city's life and how citizens connect with their surroundings on a regular basis.

Voices of Concern

This theme brings out the issues and challenges that citizens face in their day-to-day lives such as poor infrastructure, lack of public transport, disappearing green spaces, water or waste management issues, safety concerns, or loss of cultural heritage.

Places of Belonging

Places of Belonging are spaces that hold emotional, cultural, or social significance for residents. This theme focuses on spaces that provide identity, memory, and a sense of home, the places where we feel connected, seen, and grounded.

Dreams for Tomorrow

Dreams for Tomorrow reflects citizens' aspirations for the city's future. This theme brings forward ideas, hopes, and solutions imagined by the people who live in and care for the city.

Why this Vision Document?

Bhilai has its own distinct identity. It is this identity that binds its people together as one, and I am an integral part of that identity. An identity in which I take immense pride. Moreover, this is not a singular identity; rather, it manifests in myriad forms whether people choose to call Bhilai "Mini India" or the "City of Steel." Indeed, the people of Bhilai are the true embodiment of the city's character be it during a morning walk at the Biodiversity Park or while savoring *Nanhe's Tea* in the evening. These moments may not constitute grand narratives, but they are replete with anecdotes and vignettes that are often seen unfolding dynamically within these very spaces.

Defining the role of our city with exploring the experiences of citizens, creating knowledge to drive meaningful action this document divide into four parts. Part one explains everyday life in Bhilai, the relationship of citizens with city, Part two talks about their Places of Belonging and Part three focuses on the Concern related to their everyday life and Part four highlights aspiration of the citizens.

....continued on next page

In this Vision document of the City, we have attempted to address the chasm in the relationship between the policy and the reality on the ground in terms of our city. In this exercise, the aim is to look into the twin nature of Bhilai as both creators as well as victims in the broader spectrum of governance and the citizens. We encourage the citizens to become part of this study and work collectively towards a renewed vision for the future of Bhilai. We feel that stakeholders at all levels can make a considerable difference by making use of the knowledge that emerges from understanding the city's challenges.

This Vision Document serves as an expression of our city's needs and future aspirations of the people who inhabit it, and of their hopes. It is a subject presented here for discussion among citizens and policymakers alike; through this document, we seek to articulate our deep attachment, love, and commitment to the struggle for our city. It is hoped that this report can do more than just raise awareness; it can start a dialogue on the issues related to the impact of contemporary challenges on Bhilai, something that is currently absent from the conversation.

Meet Bhilai

Bhilai is the mirror of diversity, an embodiment of unity, and a city of steel, here examples of “unity in diversity” are reflected across society, culture, and even in the iron ore embedded within the steel itself. With time, Bhilai grew into one of India’s largest iron and steel plants, bearing witness to this transformation echoed in its slogan, “SAIL connected to everyone’s life.”

Bhilai Established in 1955 to fulfill the aspirations of an independent India, Bhilai is counted among the country’s major planned cities after Chandigarh. A key feature of this city is the easy availability of markets, hospitals, and essential facilities within close proximity. Maitri Bagh, located in the Maroda Sector, is not only one of Central India’s largest zoos but also a symbol of Indo-Russian friendship. Bhilai feels like a sense of comfort almost a habit one grows into. Whether it is the Gurudwara in Nehru Nagar or the temple in Sector 9, there is a lasting image of Bhilai that resides in people’s minds, which I would like to express through a slogan “Clean Bhilai, Green Bhilai.”

Bhilai is known as 'Mini India' for its diverse heritage. it was once the first choice for students and was widely recognized as an “education hub.” Although this image has somewhat faded in recent years, the Bhilai Steel Plant an integral part of the lives of its residents continues to give the city a renewed identity.

Despite the many challenges present in the city, it in stills in me a sense of acceptance and belonging. This document is dedicated to the citizens whose unwavering love for this city transforms Bhilai from merely a name on the map into a living, breathing entity. It presents a balanced perspective between the needs of the past and the aspirations of the future; a combined roadmap reflecting its evolving character and the demand for transit-oriented development. It brings together insights gathered through conversations with diverse residents capturing their everyday lives, their places of belonging, their voices of concern, and their aspirations for the city.

Meet Bhilai

Bhilai: Facts in brief

State	Chhattisgarh
District	Durg
Population	10,64,222
Area	357 sq km
Type of City Government	(Municipal Corporation Nagar Nigam)
Languages prevalent	Hindi Chhattisgarhi
Administrative Division	Bhilai divide into three administrative areas <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Bhilai Nagar Municipal Corporation2. Rishali Municipal Corporation3. Bhilai Charoda Municipal Corporation

Meet Bhialai's Citizens

In a busy shopping complex in Supela, some women are mopping the floor. I am sitting on the stairs there, waiting for someone. Just then, a middle-aged woman passes by me and asks through gestures what happened. I shake my head to say “nothing,” and she goes back to her work. After a while, when she returns, I speak with her. She must be around 52 years old, and she has been working in this shopping complex for nearly the past 12 years, doing sweeping and mopping. She tells me that she lives in a rented house nearby. Earlier, they had their own house, but it was lost due to the expenses of her husband's treatment. She wakes up daily at 4:30, finishes her household chores, and then comes here to do cleaning work. The salary is very modest, but at this age, she does not really have any other option. In this nearly 45-minute conversation, I try to see the city through her eyes. For someone from the lower-income class, especially a woman, this city is nothing less than a daily struggle how much effort it takes, even at this age.

The second story is about a social activist. When I went to meet him, he was offering his evening Namaaz. After a short while, I met him and our conversation began. He told me that he wakes up early in the morning, does household work, and then goes to people's homes to check on their problems and discuss contemporary issues. Through these conversations, he understands what problems exist and where help can be provided. He spends almost the entire day doing this. He also has his own shop; in the evening, he stays there and manages his business. Every day, he has to travel several kilo-meters. He explains how the landscape of this city is gradually changing. Most of his time goes into interacting with people and engaging in spirituality. And He has now lost faith in the government machinery; he speaks to people about spiritual and practical transformation.

It was lunchtime; everyone had finished eating and left. The field workers were getting ready for the second half. The person I spoke to was responsible for Ward 21 –waste collection. She has been doing this work for the past two years. In Ward 21, people keep their waste segregated, so there isn't much difficulty. But now, the responsibility of the Swachh Bharat Mission has been given by the municipal corporation to a contractor, and since then the working hours have increased. The salary is also very low. Every day, six days a week, she works from morning till evening. She worries about where she would go in case of an emergency, because the contractor does not provide social security like insurance. Every day, she faces many difficulties;

Glossary and Local Terms

Mini India	A place representing diverse cultures from across India
BSP	Bhilai Steel Plant
CC	Civic Center
City of Steel	A city known for its steel industry
Maitri Bagh	“Garden of Friendship”; a zoo and public park in Bhilai
SAIL	Steel Authority of India Limited
Chowpatty-style space	Open public space with street food and social activity
Kala Mandir	Cultural auditorium; Mahatma Gandhi Kala Mandir
Chitra Mandir	Former cinema hall in Bhilai
Namaaz	Islamic prayer
JanBhagidari]	Public participation in governance
Bastis	Informal settlements or slum areas
Ward	Administrative division within a city
Swachh Bharat Mission	Government cleanliness campaign in India
PPP	Public-Private Partnership; collaboration between government and private sector
Company Town	A town largely dependent on one company for services and economy
Heat Dome	A weather phenomenon trapping heat over an area
Groundwater Table	Underground water level
Service Roads	Smaller roads running parallel to highways
Sector Areas	Planned residential divisions in Bhilai
Informal Economy	Economic activities not formally regulated
Commons	Shared public spaces
Monetisation	Converting public assets into sources of revenue
Neoliberal Trends	Economic shift toward privatization and reduced state control
Retention Policy	Policy affecting continuation or retention
Synthetic Track	Artificial running track for athletics
Last-mile connectivity	Final part of a journey from transport hub to destination
Urban Commons	Record of shared public spaces
Registry	
Walkability	Ease and safety of walking in an area
Non-motorized transport	Transport without engines
Outsourcing	Hiring external agencies for services
Social Contract	Implicit agreement between citizens and institutions
Privatization	Transfer of services or assets from public to private sector

WETLAND BIODIVERSITY PARK

TALPURI (BHILAI-DURG)

Everyday Life

Everyday Life

Living in Bhilai: A City of Steel and Stories

A city passing through a stagnant past!

It is morning; the train arriving from the direction of Dallirajhara has already pulled in, and a few people are standing in clusters near the Maroda overbridge. Meanwhile, on Central Avenue and Forest Avenue, vehicles are speeding towards the Plant, while a scattered few have stepped out for a walk in the soft morning sunlight.

Shailja Bahadur (Professor) describing her daily routine in Bhilai notes that, compared to the past, the city now feels significantly more congested. She commutes to her college daily by car and has observed that traffic volumes have increased; moreover, she feels that the roads have become risky due to reckless driving. **Bhupesh Sahu (Govt. Employee)** Sharing his experiences, he says, Bhilai's good roads support daily mobility, but **reliance on private vehicles** has grown since the city bus service ended, with service roads causing discomfort from pollution.

During conversations with various people, it emerged that individuals tend to park their vehicles indiscriminately, causing significant difficulties for commuters. Furthermore, roads in certain areas are in poor condition (like service roads near highway or the

Image: Beautiful trail to walk in a Biodiversity
(Credit: Aayush)

EVERYDAY LIFE

stretches inside sector areas) a situation often met with the common complaint: "*They fix up the main roads but leave the lanes and bylanes as they are, claiming there are currently budget constraints.*"

In Bhilai, one encounters both types of contrasts: in some places, planed sector area experiences absolute tranquility and lush greenery, while in Supela and Khursipaar feels scorching sun, dust-laden air, and the loud roar of vehicles. The everyday life of Bhilai is a **vibrant blend of many different hues.**

The citizens of Bhilai shared that they prefer to visit a Temple, Gurudwara, or mosque as part of their daily routine. Bhilai offers a multitude of venues for spiritual observance sites that are not only inclusive but also serve as excellent exemplars of the region's cultural fabric, such as the Gurudwara in Nehru Nagar or the Jama Masjid and Jain Temple in Sector 6. Over the past few years, a palpable sense of cultural fervor has been witnessed throughout Bhilai on the occasion of every festival.

Image 01: Weekly Market Ruanbandha

Image 02: Gurudwara Nehru Nagar

EVERYDAY LIFE

Image: Jama Masjid Sector-6

Every evening, people from a large section of Bhilai can be seen at the Civic Center; for the residents of Bhilai, a visit to the Civic Center is an integral part of their daily routine no work, no worries, just a few friends and the Civic Center! The area also serves as a source of livelihood for many people, who primarily belong to the informal economy. The Civic Center is not merely a public hangout spot; it is, in fact, the very soul of Bhilai.

If policymakers look closely at these patterns, it becomes clear that Bhilai cannot be planned with a one-size-fits-all approach. Different areas of the city function in different ways, and each needs its own context-specific planning. Mobility is becoming a growing concern, with increasing dependence on private vehicles, weak last-mile connectivity, and the absence of reliable public transport, pointing to the need for better transport systems and traffic management.

The informal economy is not temporary but an essential part of everyday life, with street vendors and small workers supporting the city's functioning. This calls for recognition, basic protections, and planned spaces for them to operate. At the same time, while main roads often receive attention, smaller lanes and bylanes are frequently neglected, even though these are the spaces residents interact with the most.

Cultural and religious places also play a deeper role in the city, acting as spaces of connection and support rather than just worship. Overall, Bhilai appears to be gradually moving beyond its identity as just an industrial town, evolving into a more layered socio-cultural city something that future planning needs to acknowledge.

Places of Belonging

Places of Belonging

I asked Dhriti: "If there were a place in this city that were to vanish tomorrow, what would the city lose?" her answer was: "The Civic Center." I then pressed further: "Why is that?" and reply was: "You would be stripping our city of its very soul. If this city feels alive, then the Civic Center is its manifestation."

Image: Arjun Chariot Civic Center (CC)

We see Civic Center as more than just an architectural landmark it remains Bhilai's original shopping, hangout, and cultural hub, built for the steel-plant township and still alive as a "chowpatty-style" public space. It blends market, street food, gardens, and open-air events into one walkable zone. Nearby, a small Monument Park with

Image: Monument Park Civic Center (tribute to pioneers, landmark, local pride)

PLACES OF BELONGING

steel sculptures and rows of street food, and momo stalls add to its vibrant, local flavor. Even with malls like Surya Treasure Island, the Civic Center endures as Bhilai's signature public realm where culture meets relaxation, and the city's true life is experienced.

Speaking about the Civic Center, **Aayush** notes that his home is not far from the area. The "*Civic Center constitutes an integral part of Bhilai's identity*", representing a harmonious blend of the city's past and its modernity. This venue serves as the perfect spot for citizens to gather collectively. Whenever visitors come to meet him, he invariably takes them on a tour of the Civic Center.

Lukeshwari and Dhriti, for their part, state that they require no specific reason to visit the Civic Center; they simply drop by to hang out on a whim perhaps saying, "*Let's go for a stroll where? CC!*" or "*Let's meet up today*"(and we understand where).

Chitra Mandir was originally a dedicated cinema hall within Bhilai's Civic Center, later converted into the multi-purpose auditorium now known as Mahatma Gandhi Kala Mandir (often shortened to Kala Mandir). It sits at the edge of Civic Center in Sector 5.

Image: Mahatma Gandhi kala mandir CC

Mr. Duleshwar Prasad Sahu (Senior Citizen) recalls the Civic Center beginning as two simple rows of shops, with an enclosed theatre to the east once the area's only

PLACES OF BELONGING

air-conditioned cinema. Reflecting on his BSP days, he remembers watching newly released films there with his family, a memory that now makes the decline of Chitramandir feel deeply poignant.

Mr. Abhay K. Soni (Councillor) describes the Civic Center as the historic core of “social activities, entertainment, and shopping,” once featuring a garden with a toy train and, to the east, a stage now known as the Open-Air Theatre. Today, the Mahatma Gandhi Kala Mandir stands as a key cultural venue, hosting major music programmes, festivals, and public events.

In recent years, Bhilai’s Kala Mandir has reaffirmed its role as a central cultural venue, hosting large-scale events hailed as perhaps the region’s biggest musical gathering and a Lata Mangeshkar tribute concert in February. Regularly chosen by BSP-linked and city-level organisations for annual functions, commemorations, and performances, the venue continues to serve as a well-equipped, accessible auditorium supporting a steady flow of public and private cultural programmes.

Bhilai’s entertainment landscape has shifted with the rise of multiplexes like PVR at Surya Treasure Island, drawing routine audiences away from single-screen halls such as the old Chitra Mandir. As it evolved into Kala Mandir, its role moved from everyday cinema to a symbolic cultural space for music, theatre, and public gatherings quietly reflecting a sense of loss alongside adaptation. Operating within a fragile ecosystem of rising costs, policy control, and changing lifestyles, it endures as part of Bhilai’s transition its future resting on continued use, institutional support, and recognition as a shared cultural space.

Image: Shri Shiddhi Vinayak Mandir Sector-5

PLACES OF BELONGING

During conversations with a housewife, I would ask her where you go out with their families on weekends; her answer was Maitri Bagh.

Maitri Bagh is Bhilai's "Garden of Friendship" and main zoo cum-park, as a symbol of Indo-Soviet friendship and still used heavily as a picnic, leisure and education space. Local residents and BSP townships use it as an everyday green space: morning evening walks, jogging, relaxation and photography. Families, school groups and tourists treat it as a picnic and education spot zoo visit, boating, toy-train rides (not functional now) and fountain show.

Tilleshwari (housewife) recalls still visiting Maitri Bagh with her family, while many others tie their childhood memories to its once-vibrant spaces now marked by fewer animals and declining maintenance. As both an emotional and social refuge, its future calls for careful, sensitive development, since over-commercialisation risks eroding its inclusive character and displacing the very communities that have long found comfort in it.

"It may not be glamorous, but it is deeply connected with old memories and reunions with friends." - Mrs. Shailja (for Indian Coffee House, Sector 10)

Voices of Concern

Voices of Concern

Welfare Concern

Education, healthcare, and recreation have played a significant role in shaping the urban fabric of Bhilai most notably the Sector 9 Hospital, to which people travel from far and wide to seek medical treatment. However, local residents believe that amidst the changing landscape, the public-welfare-oriented image of the Bhilai Steel Plant has faded and become tarnished.

BSP and SAIL's shift toward cost-cutting, asset monetisation, and PPPs aligned with broader neoliberal trends and the National Monetisation Pipeline is locally seen not merely as reform but as a threat to the long-standing "company town" social contract that ensured affordable services. Protests, debates, and campaigns reflect concerns over rising costs, exclusion, erosion of workers' rights, and weakening accountability in essential service.

Concerns about fee hikes, new retention policy and exclusion are raised by township citizens,

"If everything becomes privatized, where will we go?" – Local residents (source-local news)

ABSP-linked remark often recalled in local discussions "हम स्टील बनाने आए हैं, स्कूल अस्पताल चलाने नहीं" ("We came to make steel, not to run schools and hospitals") captures a visible shift toward a core-business focus. On the ground, this is felt less as policy and more as a

quiet reshaping of everyday life: rising fees, job insecurity, and reduced access blending with a deeper sense of losing Bhilai's identity as a welfare-driven township. What once felt like assured, community-linked services is gradually turning into a pay-based system, where education, healthcare, and recreation seem less like rights and more like commodities.

What residents feel, including retired workers, this change unfolds in small, almost unnoticed steps schools, hospitals, and public spaces slowly altering the city's social fabric. In a city so closely tied to BSP, such decisions ripple directly into daily life, often without much local say. As this transition continues, it not only raises concerns of growing inequality and fading security for younger generations but also leaves citizens quietly negotiating whether Bhilai's welfare legacy can still be preserved or reimagined.

It saddens me when I see neglected grounds, shrinking markets, and the demands of the future a time when, perhaps, only the structures will remain, and not the city itself.

Transforming Geography: Micro Climate and Urban Risk

Every year, Bhilai experiences heat more intense than the last, and often we feels as though the summer has arrived ahead of schedule. A glance at Bhilai's geography reveals that over the past few years, there has been a surge in the demand for residential land, accompanied by rapid construction activity. Mr. **Pankaj Yadav** (private business) noted that residential complexes are being developed at a brisk pace in the outskirts of Bhilai.

VOICES OF CONCERN

Furthermore, investments have increased due to the Bharatmala project, leading to an expansion of industrial zones surrounding Bhilai; consequently, the city is gradually transforming into a "heat dome." –

Image: Garbage at Roadside

In recent years, the available groundwater in Bhilai has also seen a rise in contamination levels; moreover, due to the population's heavy reliance on groundwater, the water table has plummeted significantly falling far below the national average over the past few years.

People of Bhilai increasingly feel that “summers are getting harsher and water is getting worse,” a concern echoed by environmentalists, scientists, local media, and we everyday citizens who face rising heat, polluted rivers, and uncertain groundwater. **This concern persists because** industrial expansion, urbanisation, rural push factor, weak enforcement, and climate change are all working together, creating a cycle where heat and water problems keep worsening faster than solutions are implemented

Because these issues are both systemic and shaped by individual choices like increasing reliance on groundwater as surface water declines they cannot be solved through isolated technical fixes. With industrial growth, land-use changes, weak governance, and everyday survival decisions all reinforcing the problem as the root causes remain largely unchanged year after year.

VOICES OF CONCERN

Infrastructural Concern: The Disorder of the System

A regular commuter in Bhilai explains how everyday travel has become exhausting and unpredictable, mirroring a broader reality in which reliance on private vehicles continues to grow and public transportation has all but collapsed. Beyond this, there are obvious gaps between planned sectors and neglected bastis, internal roads are still broken despite well-maintained main highways, and problems like leaking, waste mismanagement, dust, and pollution continue.

For the past four years, I have been traveling along the service road almost every day stretch extending from Jharokha Palace to D-Mart and it remains in a poor State, a resident observes. These issues, which are raised by people of all ages and socioeconomic backgrounds, persist because they are encountered on a daily basis and advancements are still scarce and uneven.

*During my daily commute from home to college, I noticed numerous uneven speed breakers scattered along the route from Shankar Nagar to Smriti Nagar. This issue is not limited to Smriti Nagar alone; there are many locations across Bhilai where speed breakers have been constructed arbitrarily, - **Rajyavardhan Singh (Youth)**.*

Across conversations, citizens of Bhilai including lower-income groups share that the poor state of public transport feels exhausting in their daily lives, often leaving them feeling overlooked, as the system does not seem inclusive or supportive of their needs, also public transport regulated by private players does not have option of pass system

for daily commuters this also raises an lack of options and monetary concern for students and lower income group peoples.

VOICES OF CONCERN

Image: Abundant Commons- Ranga Talaab

Wandering livestock in Bhilai pose an ongoing issue for infrastructure, leading to increased traffic jams, road mishaps, and unsatisfactory sanitation, while highlighting deficiencies in regulation and city planning. Although there are occasional initiatives to address the issue, insufficient accountability and the merging of rural and urban practices result in the issue resurfacing, turning it into a daily risk to safety and public health, particularly for at-risk road users.

Stray Cows problem in Bhilai

Animal Feeding Zone in various location

*Beyond human inconvenience, it raises animal welfare concerns, as many cattle are abandoned once they become unproductive, left to survive on garbage, face accidents or live in overcrowded shelters – **Lukeshwari (NGO)***

Meanwhile, **Shrikant**, a professor working in Sector 6, argues that rather than constructing new facilities merely to demonstrate development, priority should be given to the existing infrastructure specifically those elements that are currently in a dilapidated state. Citing the severely damaged roads in the sector area as an example, he asserts, "**These need to be repaired first; that is the more pressing priority.**"

He also expressed concern that corruption is endemic to virtually all such infrastructure projects, a factor that ultimately compromises the quality of the work performed.

VOICES OF CONCERN

Different groups experience infrastructure in distinct ways: youth struggle with poor transport, lack of sports facilities, and migration pressures; women highlight safety, accessibility, and the burden of inadequate local infrastructure; senior citizens emphasise the loss of parks and walkable spaces; workers face long, costly commutes and unsafe working environments; and small vendors suffer from shrinking public markets and changing urban patterns. Despite these differences, all groups are connected by a shared dependence on basic infrastructure for dignity and daily survival.

An International Athlete from Bhilai states that while Bhilai possesses all the necessary facilities for sports and has even produced numerous international athletes it still lacks a synthetic track. He points out that even smaller cities like Jagdalpur have synthetic tracks, yet Bhilai does not; furthermore, the grounds in Bhilai lack inclusive facilities. Although he has repeatedly petitioned the administration regarding this matter, no progress has been made.

Image : Athletics Academy Forest Avenue

This concern persists because Bhilai's infrastructure is shaped by a mix of systemic issues like fragmented governance, unequal investment, and environmental neglect, along with individual choices such as rising dependence on private vehicles, creating a cycle where problems reinforce each other and remain unresolved.

These concerns reveal that Bhilai is at a critical transition point, the issues are partly systemic, rooted in planning structures, BSP-municipal fragmentation, and policy priorities that favour large projects over everyday infrastructure, and partly incidental, shaped by specific administrative delays, local decisions, and implementation failures. Ultimately, the persistence of these infrastructural concerns shows that without integrated planning, stronger accountability, and active citizen participation, Bhilai risks drifting further away from its inclusive and well-managed urban foundation.

Dreams for Tomorrow

Dreams for Tomorrow

Public Transport and Mobility

चलते चलते यूँ ही रुक जाता हूँ मैं, मंजिल नहीं आई बस फुटपाथ खतम हो गया

! translate to I stop walking just like that simply because the sidewalk has come to an end. Only the footpath has ended not the road itself. There are many such places in Bhilai where the footpath abruptly comes to a halt midway; in some spots, it becomes extremely narrow, while in others, it turns uneven and rugged. Citizens do not explicitly state this, yet conversations I held with them reveal that the majority of people are demanding better sidewalks specifically senior citizen and youth (students), walkways that feature adequate width, continuity, and a smooth surface quality and the creation of an inclusive environment for citizens specifically by making non-motorized modes of transport accessible and fully equipped with necessary facilities.

I have noticed that at many railway underbridges, reflector mirrors are not installed at blind spots, making movement risky showing how small but crucial details are often overlooked. –Rajyavardhan Singh

Since the system has only a few small flaws that can be fixed with improved implementation and follow-up rather than a significant overhaul, people think these changes are attainable. even if some regions need investment, they are viewed as long-term prospects, particularly when it comes to integrating walking and cycling to improve daily mobility and lessen traffic and pollution.

Image: Central Avenue

This optimism endures because Bhilai is perceived as a city where modest, doable improvements such as better walkways, controlled transportation, and enhanced connectivity can have a significant impact, bolstered by impending e-buses. However, there is a silent gap that coexists with this optimism: although we as individual encounter these problems on a daily basis and want change, active engagement and introspection are frequently lacking, making advancement contingent on both more citizen participation and administrative action.

DREAMS FOR TOMORROW

Preservation of Commons

There are numerous locations in Bhilai whose significance is gradually shifting rather than diminishing; their purpose and significance are changing.

In the past, some people would sit in the Model Town park, drink alcohol, and make a mess. We cleaned the area and installed fencing on our own initiative. These days, kids visit the park to play in the evenings, while older residents use it for walks in the morning. Bhilai has a lot more of these locations that require maintenance. – Hariom Tiwari (Concillor)

We resident must pay more attention to these areas by comprehending the underlying causes of this transformation, which is crucial for their preservation. People think this is possible since these locations have a strong connection to Bhilai's identity; communities may unite and use this sense of shared identity and pointing towards administration's attention to their conservation. Numerous organizations in Bhilai are already working tirelessly in this direction, and if each generation upholds this cultural legacy and serves as a live example, this hope can endure.

Simultaneously, residents must adopt a more pragmatic perspective and regard such cultural public spaces as a collective duty. In addition, the administration needs to be made more conscious of their importance and strive to maintain their vitality, activity, and accessibility within the city.

JanBhagidari “Public participation”

Roshan Ali Ansari believes that any development in the city should be carried out through collective participation along with administrative support. He emphasizes that a better city can be built when citizens have a sense of moral responsibility, basic awareness, and cooperate with the system. Therefore, he feels that citizens should actively take part in important decision-making processes of the city.

Improving cities and public welfare is a gradual and complex process, but even at the initial stage, if citizens participate in ward meetings and provide constructive feedback to their ward councillors, gradual yet meaningful change can be achieved over time.

This hope can remain alive if we see it as a process rather than an end, allowing continuous improvement over time. Mobilising people at the ward level and addressing problems through local discussion can help find practical solutions. This requires both behavioural change among citizens and greater social awareness.

In the coming five years, it is reasonable to expect visible improvements at both ward and city levels. The need here is less for large structural changes and more for social and administrative shifts, which can begin at the individual level. This responsibility lies with both we as citizens and ward-level urban bodies (Govt. + Civil Society) to ensure that the process becomes more inclusive, especially for women and the elderly.

At a surface level, it appears that the main obstacle to these ambitions is the failure of the administrative system. However, at a deeper level, it involves a lack of public participation, limited citizen engagement, low awareness, poor planning & weak implementation, lack of coordination among officials, and social or economic inequalities. Together, these factors highlight the larger gap between the city's aspirations and its realities.

Policy Insights

Policy Insights: What the city is telling us?

1. Mobility and everyday accessibility

The roads are generally good, according to the locals, but walking is dangerous and public transportation is inconsistent, making non vehicle users spend more time, money, and be at more risk. Gaps in design, regulation, and follow-up such as inadequate junction planning, a lack of safety measures, lax fare management, and disregard for non-motorized users are more problematic than large-scale projects.

Short-term:

Set transparent vehicle tolls with basic service standards, fix black spots (mirrors, speed calming, lights), and fix important pedestrian routes (near schools, markets, and hospitals).

Medium-term:

Track basic mobility indicators, develop ward-level walkability/cycling plans, and integrate the e-bus system (clear routes, frequent service, safe stops, last-mile connectivity).

Long-term:

Adopt a "small city mobility" strategy that emphasizes bicycling, walking, and reasonably priced public transportation; incorporate universal access and safety into all road designs; and coordinate mobility with land-use planning.

Key stakeholders

Bhilai Nagar Nigam (municipal corporation), Traffic Police, State Urban Development Department, Transport Department, ward councillors, auto and e-bus operators' associations, resident groups, disability rights groups, schools and colleges.

2. Public spaces, environmental health and the urban commons

Public spaces like Maitri Bagh, Civic Centre, neighborhood parks, and the dams, have been considered the emotional centers of the city. Nevertheless, there are instances where residents notice a decline in maintenance, lack of vegetation, pollution, overcrowding, and commercialization, especially within crucial public spaces associated with the BSP. The profit-oriented activities, including monetization, price hikes, or privatization of the commons, pose risks for the exclusion of the dependent communities.

Immediate steps include improving cleanliness, repairs, and making them inclusive for all in critical urban commons such as Traffic Parks greening at a nominal cost (through planting trees and providing shading areas), and organising concerted campaigns for stray cattle and waste. Mid-term measures should involve setting up an Urban Commons Registry to determine ownership of these commons, enhance maintenance budgets in collaboration with the communities, and initiate monitoring of air quality and noise pollution with punitive measures for violation. In the long term, major commons must be protected through legal means from any damaging form of privatization, and an urban ecology approach must become part of city-planning efforts.

POLICY INSIGHTS

Key stakeholders

BSP/SAIL, Bhilai Nagar Nigam, State Urban and Environment Departments, Pollution Control Board, urban development authorities, local park and market committees, cultural organisations, environmental groups, animal-welfare groups.

3. Welfare infrastructure, education and social protection under pressure

The welfare city of Bhilai, which was known for its industries and hospitals with subsidized amenities, seems to be taking on a new turn towards paying costs and privatization, leading to shut downs and out-sourcing along with issues related to health care and education being cost-based. This creates an additional burden on young people and poorer households that already have problems finding work locally and potentially migrating. On the other hand, Bhilai's education and industrial potential presents opportunity if maintained.

Immediate steps include, make sure that affordable basic services will definitely be available due to the presence of caps, discount, or subsidy in case there are PPP projects to be implemented. Conduct joint awareness campaigns regarding career opportunities and skills development programs in schools and colleges in collaboration with industrial sectors. In the medium-term, concentrate on the rehabilitation of the vital learning institutions involved in BSP by means of collaboration, create a forum for the city to address education and employment issues, and conduct a few PPP initiatives with a definite set of social obligations like caps on fees and scholarships. For the long-term, create an understanding among city residents that the responsibility of the state is to provide its citizens with quality education and healthcare.

Key stakeholders

BSP/SAIL management, State Education and Health Departments, Bhilai Nagar Nigam, school and college boards, teacher unions, parent associations, student groups, local industries and business associations.

Bibliography

1. [Urbanization and Urban Growth in India: Trends and Patterns • Sociology.Institute](#)
2. [Muddling Through Waste: Self Governance and Collective Action in the Wastewater Commons | Springer Nature Link](#)
3. Contemporary Urban Planning by John M. Levy
4. [Chhattisgarh's First Zoo Moves Toward Privatization - Dainik Jagran English](#)
5. [BSP \(भिलाई स्टील प्लांट\) धीरे-धीरे अपनी पुरानी सामाजिक सुविधाओं को ननजी क्षेत्र \(Private Sector\) को सौंप रहा है। - Indian News Service - INS](#)
6. Contextualising Mobility in Smaller Cities - Nagrika Series: Small city mobility
7. [Mobility Challenges Bhilai: Dependence on Private Transport Amid Public Transit Absence](#)
8. [Retired employees of Bhilai Steel Plant stage a massive protest, laying siege to the Municipal Ad...](#)
9. [Bhilai](#)
10. [Urban Challenge: Stray Cattle Roam City Streets, Causing Chaos](#)
11. [Stray animal management in urban India - Pashudhan Praharee | Pet Care Blog](#)
12. [BMC accelerates drive against stray animals - The Hitavada](#)
13. [Support Walking Project – Donate & Empower Safer Walking](#)
14. [Beyond infrastructure: New cities need a soul to survive](#)

Annexure

Include supporting material that strengthens your analysis, that couldn't be added fully or mentioned in the document.

Include: Interview excerpts, Municipal corporation documents, Scheme or Policy Documents, Public Notices etc.

SNO	Reference	Date of the Document
01	PaperCutting of Bhilai Patrika Link	25/02/2026
02	Padmavati (Private Employee) Through her interview, I learned just how inclusive Bhilai is for the lower-income class as well as the specific struggles they face, their sense of acceptance within the city, and other such aspects.	

Fellowship was partly supported by :

Tikendra Sahu

Tikendra is from Bhilai, Chhattisgarh and is a B.Tech graduate and freelance software developer with a passion for exploration, research, and writing. Alongside his graduation, he has remained actively involved in grassroots initiatives and continues to observe and understand the changes unfolding around him. Beyond systems and software, he carries a creative spirit one that finds expression in writing and artistic pursuits. He values these spaces as a way to reflect, to understand, and to express himself in ways that go beyond structured thinking.

Blending technical skill with human sensitivity, he continues to explore paths where innovation meets empathy, and where small efforts can create meaningful change.

Nāgrika Fellowship Coordinator:

Praisya David | Research Associate

Creative Commons
Attribution 4.0 International

www.nagrika.org

Message from the Founders

Ten years ago, we set off on a journey across India's small towns. Over five months and fifty cities, we came through stories, crafts, silences, and dreams. We rediscovered that our smaller cities were not merely settlements; they were living archives of collective memory and identity—fossils of space and time inhabited by breath and imagination.

In Ratnagiri we were directed by many city experts to meet an auto mechanic. He was the go-to person for everyone in the city, including the city government, for engineering issues such as the city's water supply. He had seen the city evolve and remembered its various extensions, its water supply networks, and the various issues the city had faced in the last few decades. In Thanjavur, we sat with a veena-maker working 20-hour days in a modest shed, carving centuries of musical tradition into a single piece of jackfruit wood. We listened to bakers, poets, priests, and students. They told us not only what their cities were, but what they could become.

What struck us most was this: citizens carry the city's soul. The insights they hold—about its past, its present, and its future—are powerful, yet rarely represented in how cities are imagined or governed. This realization gave genesis to the Nāgrika Fellowship. It has been our attempt to honour the power of local voices—to create space for young people to observe, listen, document, and co-create city narratives from within. Each City Vision Document is not just a reflection of one fellow's journey; it's a collaborative act of remembering and imagining.

We hope this document stirs dialogue, ownership, and pride. And just like cities that shape their people, we hope this fellowship shapes a new kind of citizen—curious, rooted, and ready to lead.

We exist to ensure small-city voices, often unheard, have the knowledge and tools to influence the development and policies of their communities.

We focus on citizen-driven research. By engaging directly with small city communities, we present their authentic realities, untouched by outside narratives. This hands-on approach keeps small city voices at the heart of everything we do.

Citizen-Centred

It's always about the people. Small-city citizens are at the heart of everything we do.

Curious and Objective

Our approach stems from curiosity—focusing on the truth, making sure every voice in small cities is heard clearly and fairly.

Credible and Rooted

We are committed to producing knowledge and insight from the small cities that is dependable and high-quality.

Resourceful

We make the most of what we have, using our resources wisely to create valuable knowledge.

Small Cities, Big Love

Creative Commons
Attribution 4.0 International

www.nagrika.org